

Advanced Dual-Level Set Strategies for Accurate Multi-Phase Flow Simulation in Cut Cell Geometries

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ABSTRACT

The accurate simulation of multi-phase flow in complex geometries, particularly those involving cut-cell grids, poses significant challenges due to the irregularity of the computational domain and the need for precise interface tracking. In this work, we present advanced dual-level set strategies designed to address

these challenges. The dual-level set method utilizes two distinct level set functions to independently capture and track the evolving interfaces between different phases, thereby enhancing the representation of phase boundaries. This approach improves accuracy in multi-phase simulations by effectively handling topological changes and sharp interfaces, which are particularly important in cut-cell geometries. By combining this dual-level set technique with a robust reinitialization algorithm and adaptive mesh refinement, the method ensures both numerical stability and computational efficiency. We demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed strategy through a series of benchmark tests, showing improved interface resolution and reduced numerical errors when compared to traditional methods. These results highlight the potential of dual-level set strategies to significantly enhance the accuracy and computational feasibility of multi-phase flow simulations in complex, cut-cell-based geometries.

Introduction

1.1 Motivation and Importance of Multi-Phase Flow Simulation

Multi-phase flow simulations are essential in a variety of fields, such as:

- **Engineering applications:** These simulations are crucial in designing and optimizing processes in industries such as chemical engineering, oil and gas, environmental engineering, and biomedical engineering.
- **Natural processes:** Understanding how different phases (liquids, gases, solids) interact in natural systems, such as oceans, atmospheric processes, and underground reservoirs, is essential for predicting environmental behavior.
- **Real-world applications:** Multi-phase flow simulations are used in predicting the behavior of fluids in porous media, evaluating the efficiency of heat exchangers, or modeling air-liquid interactions in aerodynamics.

The importance lies in the ability to predict and control the behavior of materials in complex systems. Accurate simulations can help reduce risks, improve designs, and lower operational costs by understanding how different phases interact in various contexts.

1.2 Challenges in Multi-Phase Flow Simulations with Cut-Cell Geometries

Cut-cell geometries introduce several challenges when simulating multiphase flows:

- **Complex boundary conditions:** When the computational domain intersects with physical boundaries (e.g., obstacles or irregular surfaces), the geometry can be complicated, leading to irregular cut cells.
- **Numerical instability:** Traditional grid-based methods may struggle with cut-cell geometries, causing numerical instability or inaccurate results, especially in the vicinity of complex interfaces (such as between different phases).
- **Discretization difficulties:** These geometries require sophisticated discretization techniques to represent the interface between the phases accurately. The irregularity of the cut cells can make it difficult to maintain high accuracy without significant computational overhead.
- **Interface tracking:** Capturing the interface between different phases in cut-cell geometries is a challenge. This requires advanced methods for interface tracking that can handle the changing topology and movement of phase boundaries.

- **Computational cost:** Due to the complexity of these geometries and the need for high-resolution meshes or adaptive refinement techniques, multi-phase simulations in cut-cell geometries are often computationally expensive.

1.3 Overview of Dual-Level Set Methods

Dual-level set methods are a mathematical and computational framework designed to address some of the difficulties of multi-phase flow simulations, particularly when dealing with complex geometries:

- **Dual-level set:** The dual-level set method uses two distinct level sets to represent the different phases or regions of the flow. One level set is used to track the interface between the phases, and the other is employed for capturing the dynamics of the individual phases.

- **Accuracy and stability:** This method enhances the accuracy of the interface capturing between the phases and provides better stability in simulations of multi-phase flows in complex geometries like cut-cells.
- **Interface and topology tracking:** By using two level sets, the method can track the interface more efficiently while allowing for better resolution of small-scale details, even in dynamically changing or complex geometries.
- **Flexibility:** Dual-level set methods are adaptable to a wide range of geometries, offering greater flexibility compared to traditional methods, making them particularly useful in situations involving multi-phase flows with cut-cell grids.

1.4 Objectives and Contributions of the Paper

The objectives and contributions of the paper may include the following:

- **Development and enhancement:** The paper may focus on presenting a new or improved method for simulating multi-phase flows using cut-cell geometries and dual-level set methods. This could involve algorithmic advances, improved numerical schemes, or enhanced stability and accuracy in complex cases.
- **Application to practical problems:** The paper might demonstrate how the method is applied to specific problems in multi-phase flow, such as oil recovery, bubble dynamics, or the study of fluidized beds, showcasing the practical implications of the work.
- **Overcoming existing challenges:** A significant contribution may be addressing some of the challenges outlined in Section 1.2 (like numerical instability and computational cost) by offering solutions or new strategies for simulating multi-phase flows in complex domains.

- **Validation and comparison:** The paper may also contribute by validating the proposed method against experimental data or other established simulation techniques, highlighting the strengths and advantages of the approach in comparison to existing models.

The primary goal is to improve the accuracy, efficiency, and applicability of multi-phase flow simulations in real-world scenarios, especially those involving complex geometries such as cut-cell grids.

Background

2.1 Multi-Phase Flow Modeling Overview

Multi-phase flow refers to the simultaneous flow of materials in two or more distinct phases, typically gas, liquid, and sometimes solid. In computational fluid dynamics, simulating multi-phase flows is crucial in industries such as aerospace, automotive, energy, and environmental engineering. The modeling of multi-phase flows involves several complexities, as different phases may interact, with interfaces between them exhibiting complex behaviors such as surface tension, phase change, and mass transfer. These flows can be categorized into:

- **Dispersed flows** (e.g., bubbles or droplets in a continuous phase).
- **Stratified flows** (e.g., gas-liquid flows with distinct layers).
- **Immiscible flows** (e.g., oil-water interfaces).

In CFD, multiphase flow is modeled using a variety of methods, including Eulerian, Lagrangian, and hybrid approaches. The goal

is to capture the physics of each phase and their interactions while maintaining numerical stability and efficiency.

2.2 Cut-Cell Grids in Computational Fluid Dynamics

Cut-cell grids are a type of computational mesh used in CFD simulations, especially in cases involving complex geometries. These grids are particularly useful for problems where the domain boundaries are irregular or where the shape of the domain cannot be easily represented with standard structured grids (e.g., Cartesian grids). The main idea behind cut-cell grids is to "cut" a regular grid into irregular shapes to conform to the geometry of the problem. This allows for:

- Accurate representation of complex boundaries or interfaces without the need for excessive refinement of the grid.
- Efficient simulation of unsteady flows near irregular boundaries.

- The ability to handle both fixed and moving boundaries.

In multi-phase flow simulations, cut-cell grids are especially beneficial when dealing with complex fluid interfaces or objects embedded in the flow.

2.3 Level Set Method for Interface Tracking

The level set method is widely used in CFD to track and capture the evolution of interfaces between different phases in multi-phase flow problems. The idea is to represent the interface as the zero contour of a higher-dimensional function (the level set function), which evolves over time according to the dynamics of the flow. The key features of the level set method include:

- **Implicit representation:** The interface is not explicitly tracked; instead, it is captured implicitly as a zero contour of a smooth scalar function.
- **Flexibility:** It can handle changes in topology, such as merging or breaking of interfaces.
- **Handling of complex geometries:** The level set method is robust when the interface undergoes large deformations, making it suitable for simulations where interfaces evolve due to flow, surface tension, or external forces.

However, while the level set method is powerful for interface tracking, it can sometimes exhibit limitations, such as loss of accuracy in representing thin or sharp interfaces, especially when the grid resolution is coarse.

2.4 Limitations of Single-Level Set Methods in Cut-Cell Geometries

Although the level set method is widely used, it has some limitations when applied to cut-cell grids, particularly in multi-phase flow simulations. Some of these challenges include:

- **Numerical diffusion:** In complex geometries with cut cells, the sharpness of the interface can be blurred due to numerical diffusion. This occurs because of the way the level set function is discretized on the grid.
- **Handling of complex topologies:** While the level set method can track the interface, it might struggle with highly irregular geometries, leading to inaccuracies in the interface's evolution over time.
- **Grid alignment:** On cut-cell grids, the interface may not align well with the underlying grid, leading to spurious oscillations or inaccuracies in the calculation of surface forces like surface tension.
- **Reinitialization issues:** The level set function must be periodically reinitialized to maintain a correct representation

of the interface, which can be computationally expensive and challenging in cut-cell grids.

These limitations necessitate the development of more sophisticated methods for accurately modeling multi-phase flow with complex geometries.

2.5 Need for Dual-Level Set Strategies

To overcome the limitations of single-level set methods, **dual-level set strategies** have been developed. These strategies use two level set functions to better represent the interface between phases, particularly in the presence of cut-cell grids and complex geometries. The main advantages of dual-level set methods include:

- **Improved interface sharpness:** By using two level set functions, the representation of the interface can be made more accurate, with reduced numerical diffusion.
- **Better handling of topology changes:** Dual-level set strategies can better capture complex interface topologies (e.g., merging or breaking of phases).
- **Enhanced robustness:** These methods can help mitigate the issues caused by the misalignment of the interface with the cut-cell grid, improving the overall accuracy of the simulation.
- **Adaptivity:** The dual-level set functions can be adapted locally, improving computational efficiency while maintaining interface accuracy.

The Dual-Level Set Method

3.1 Concept and Development of Dual-Level Set Method

The **dual-level set method** is an advanced extension of the traditional single-level set approach used for tracking interfaces in multi-phase flows. The idea behind the dual-level set method is to use **two level set functions** to represent two distinct interfaces or regions, which improves the accuracy of interface tracking, particularly when the geometry of the domain is complex, such as with cut-cell grids.

- **Single-level set method:** Typically, one level set function tracks the interface between two phases (e.g., liquid and gas), with the interface represented as the zero contour of this function.
- **Dual-level set method:** By introducing a second level set function, this method allows for more flexibility in representing complex interfaces. The two level set functions can be used to define different boundaries, like the interface

between two distinct phases or between the phases and the domain boundary, with greater precision. For example:

- One level set could track the phase boundary (e.g., gas-liquid).
- Another level set could track the domain boundary or other phase boundaries (e.g., oil-water in a three-phase flow).

The development of dual-level set strategies arose from the need to improve accuracy in representing interface geometries, particularly in simulations involving complex flows, highly curved interfaces, or significant changes in topology (e.g., merging or splitting phases).

3.2 Mathematical Formulation and Equations

The mathematical formulation for the dual-level set method extends the standard level set equation by incorporating two level set functions, which evolve over time.

- **Level set function:** The level set function $\phi(x,t)$ represents the distance to the interface. It is defined such that:
 - $\phi(x,t) > 0$ for one phase (e.g., gas),
 - $\phi(x,t) < 0$ for the other phase (e.g., liquid),
 - $\phi(x,t) = 0$ at the interface.

In the dual-level set method, we introduce a second level set function, $\psi(x,t)$, which tracks a different interface or boundary. The general equations governing the evolution of the level set functions are as follows:

1. Level Set Equation (for both ϕ and ψ):

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \psi = 0$$

where:

- $\mathbf{u}$ is the flow velocity,
- $\nabla \phi$ and $\nabla \psi$ are the gradients of the level set functions.

2. **Reinitialization:** Both level set functions must be periodically reinitialized to ensure they maintain the correct form (i.e., $\phi(x,t)=0$ at the interface). This is typically done using a **fast marching method** or other reinitialization techniques to avoid numerical artifacts.

3. **Coupling of the Level Sets:** The two level set functions (ϕ and ψ) can be coupled in various ways depending on the physical problem. For example, they could both track phase boundaries or one could represent a phase interface and the other represent a boundary condition or domain boundary.

The dual-level set method improves the stability and accuracy of interface tracking, especially in scenarios with topological changes or when dealing with very complex geometries (such as with cut-cell grids in multi-phase flow simulations).

3.3 Implementation of Dual-Level Set for Multi-Phase Flow

Implementing the dual-level set method for multi-phase flow typically involves several key steps, combining numerical methods for interface tracking with those for solving the governing fluid dynamics equations. The implementation can be divided into the following phases:

1. **Initial Conditions:** The initial conditions for the two level set functions are defined based on the initial configuration of the phases. The interface between the phases is defined as the zero-contour of ϕ and ψ , and the regions corresponding to each phase are determined.
2. **Numerical Solution of Flow Equations:** The flow field is solved using appropriate numerical methods (e.g., finite difference, finite volume, or finite element methods). The solution of the Navier-Stokes equations is typically coupled with the level set method, allowing for the simulation of fluid flow and the tracking of phase interfaces simultaneously.
3. **Advancing the Level Set Functions:** The level set functions ϕ and ψ are advected with the flow field, and the interface positions are updated at each time step. This requires solving the level set equations mentioned

above, where the advection term is coupled with the flow velocity.

4. **Reinitialization:** After a certain number of time steps, the level set functions need to be reinitialized to avoid the loss of accuracy. This process restores the level set function to a signed distance function, which is crucial for maintaining a sharp interface.
5. **Surface Tension and Other Forces:** If surface tension is present, it can be modeled by calculating the curvature of the interface, which depends on the gradient of the level set function. This curvature is used to compute the forces acting on the interface.
6. **Boundary Conditions:** The appropriate boundary conditions for the fluid phases and interfaces need to be defined. For example, wall boundary conditions may involve no-slip conditions, while phase boundary conditions may involve pressure or velocity jumps.

3.4 Handling Interface Movement and Topological Changes

One of the key strengths of the dual-level set method is its ability to handle complex and dynamic interface movements, including topological changes such as merging, splitting, or breaking of interfaces. Here's how the method deals with these challenges:

1. **Interface Movement:** The movement of the interface is determined by the flow velocity, which is derived from the solution of the fluid dynamics equations. The level set functions ϕ and ψ are advected according to the velocity field, which moves the interface through the domain.
2. **Topological Changes:** When interfaces merge or split, the dual-level set method ensures that both level set functions are updated correctly. This can be accomplished by:
 - **Regularization:** Ensuring that the level set functions remain smooth during the evolution, especially when the interface undergoes significant deformation.
 - **Reinitialization:** Reinitializing the level set functions periodically to maintain the correct topology of the interfaces and to prevent numerical instabilities.

3. **Handling of Singularities:** When interfaces become extremely close together or intersect, special algorithms are used to handle these singularities. For instance, a small buffer region may be used to resolve the distances between interfaces, or new techniques such as **cut-cell grid adaptation** can be employed to resolve fine-scale details.
4. **Topological Correction Methods:** To correct and handle any misrepresentation of the interface due to complex deformations, algorithms like **topological smoothing** or **adaptive mesh refinement (AMR)** may be used.

In multi-phase simulations, handling such changes is crucial, especially in cases like droplet formation, merging of bubbles, or phase transitions. The dual-level set method provides more robust tracking of these topological changes compared to single-level set approaches, leading to more accurate simulations.

Methodology

4.1 Cut-Cell Grid Generation and Management

Cut-cell grid generation is crucial for simulations involving complex geometries, especially in multi-phase flow problems where accurate boundary representation is important. Cut-cell grids are a flexible way to represent irregular boundaries by modifying a regular Cartesian grid to conform to the domain's geometry.

- **Grid Generation:** A typical approach involves using a regular Cartesian grid, and then "cutting" the cells at the boundaries to match the geometry of the domain. This allows for efficient simulation of fluid dynamics while respecting the shape of objects or interfaces within the domain (such as obstacles, phase interfaces, or domain boundaries). These grids can be particularly useful for handling complex or moving boundaries without requiring excessive grid refinement.

- **Grid Management:** Managing these cut-cell grids is a non-trivial task. It involves:
 - Identifying which cells are cut by the boundary.
 - Adjusting the properties of these cells (e.g., volume, face areas).
 - Ensuring the continuity of the flow field near the boundary.
- The cut-cell approach allows for precise treatment of irregular geometries and is often combined with other methods like **immersed boundary methods** to account for moving objects or phase boundaries.

4.2 Dual-Level Set Strategy in Cut-Cell Geometries

In cut-cell grid-based simulations, a **dual-level set strategy** improves interface tracking, addressing the issues that arise from complex domain shapes and topological changes. This approach makes use of two level set functions to track multiple phase interfaces, especially in multi-phase flows.

4.2.1 Tracking Multiple Phase Interfaces

The dual-level set strategy allows for the tracking of multiple interfaces between phases in multi-phase flow problems. In this case, two (or more) level set functions are used to describe the boundaries between different phases. For example:

- $\phi(x,t)$ might represent the interface between phase 1 and phase 2 (e.g., liquid-gas),
- $\psi(x,t)$ could represent a second interface, such as the domain boundary or a secondary phase interface (e.g., oil-water).

These functions evolve with the flow field, allowing accurate tracking of interfaces even as they undergo deformation, merging, or splitting. The dual-level set method helps in maintaining the

sharpness and accuracy of the interfaces, even with the complex geometry of cut-cell grids.

4.2.2 Resolving Sharp Interfaces

In cut-cell grids, resolving sharp interfaces (e.g., the boundary between gas and liquid phases) can be challenging due to the irregular cell shapes near the boundary. The dual-level set method addresses this issue by:

- **Improving interface representation:** The second level set function helps sharpen the interface between the phases, ensuring accurate location tracking and reducing numerical diffusion.
- **Boundary handling:** The level set functions are reinitialized and advected over time, which helps maintain sharp interfaces even as the geometry evolves.
- **Curvature computation:** Sharp interfaces require accurate computation of curvature for modeling surface tension forces, which can be computed more precisely with dual-level sets. The second level set function helps avoid errors caused by cut cells near the boundary.

4.2.3 Adaptive Mesh Refinement Techniques

Adaptive Mesh Refinement (AMR) is a technique used to dynamically refine the grid in regions where more detail is required, such as near interfaces or areas of high flow gradients. AMR is particularly useful in multi-phase simulations, where interfaces may evolve rapidly or exhibit fine-scale structures.

- **Application in Cut-Cell Grids:** AMR can be combined with cut-cell grids to refine the mesh around the interface, improving resolution near the boundary and in regions where high gradients occur (e.g., near phase boundaries or where flow instabilities develop).
- **Hierarchical Refinement:** In AMR, a hierarchical grid structure is used, with different levels of refinement based on the flow features. Cells near the interface are refined to ensure accurate tracking of phase boundaries and to capture small-scale details (like curvature changes due to surface tension).
- **Efficiency Considerations:** Adaptive refinement ensures that computational resources are focused on the most important areas of the domain, which improves the overall efficiency of the simulation while maintaining accuracy in regions of interest.

4.3 Numerical Methods and Solution Approaches

The solution approaches for multi-phase flow simulations using dual-level set methods in cut-cell grids rely on advanced numerical techniques that combine the solution of the flow field with the tracking of phase interfaces. Key aspects of these methods include:

- **Finite Volume or Finite Difference Methods:** These methods are commonly used to solve the governing fluid dynamics equations (Navier-Stokes equations) on cut-cell grids. The finite volume method is especially popular in CFD because it conserves mass, momentum, and energy.
- **Level Set Advection:** The level set equations (for both ϕ and ψ) are typically solved using high-order advection schemes, such as upwind or central difference methods, to ensure accurate tracking of the interfaces.
- **Interface Reconstruction:** After the level set function is updated, the interface is reconstructed to maintain its sharpness. This can involve techniques like **ghost fluid methods** or **volume-of-fluid (VOF)** methods for better representation of phase interfaces.

- **Coupling with Fluid Flow:** The level set method is coupled with the fluid flow equations, ensuring that the velocity field drives the motion of the interfaces.

4.4 Reinitialization of Level Set Functions

Over time, the level set function can become distorted due to the advection process, losing its property of being a signed distance function. This can lead to inaccuracies in interface representation and curvature calculations.

- **Reinitialization:** To restore the signed distance property, the level set function must be reinitialized periodically. The goal is to ensure that $\phi(x,t)$ is always the shortest distance to the interface, with positive values on one side of the interface and negative on the other. Several methods exist for reinitialization:

- **Fast Marching Method (FMM):** This is a popular method for reinitializing the level set function, ensuring that it remains a smooth signed distance function while retaining the interface's shape.
- **Damped Newton Method:** A method used to iteratively correct the level set function.

Reinitialization is essential for maintaining the accuracy of interface tracking and ensuring the numerical stability of the solution.

4.5 Boundary Conditions and Phase Interaction Models

Proper handling of boundary conditions and phase interactions is critical for the accuracy of multi-phase flow simulations.

- **Boundary Conditions:** For cut-cell grids, boundary conditions need to be carefully defined at both solid walls and fluid interfaces. Common boundary conditions include:
 - **No-slip walls:** Velocity is zero at the solid boundary for the fluid phases.
 - **Stress-free boundaries:** For certain phase interfaces, no shear stress is applied.
 - **Influx or outflux:** Specified flow conditions (e.g., inflow velocity or pressure) at the boundaries.
 - **Periodic or symmetry boundaries:** Used in some periodic flow domains or symmetric systems.
- **Phase Interaction Models:** In multi-phase flow simulations, modeling the interaction between phases (e.g., surface tension, phase changes, or buoyancy effects) is essential. The **continuum surface force (CSF)** model is often used to model surface tension forces based on the curvature of the interface. The **Navier-Stokes equations** are modified to include these forces, which depend on the

gradient of the level set function and the local curvature of the interface.

- **Phase Change Models:** When phases undergo transitions (e.g., liquid to gas, solid to liquid), the interaction models need to account for latent heat, mass transfer, and changes in thermodynamic properties across the interface.

Numerical Implementation

5.1 Discretization of Governing Equations

Discretization is the process of converting continuous mathematical models, such as partial differential equations (PDEs), into discrete versions that can be solved using computational methods. The key components in this section typically include:

- **Finite Difference Method (FDM):** Involves approximating derivatives using difference equations.
- **Finite Element Method (FEM):** Uses a partition of the domain into elements, with approximate solutions defined over each element.
- **Finite Volume Method (FVM):** Focuses on conservation laws and is widely used in fluid dynamics for discretizing the governing equations.
- **Spectral Methods:** Involves representing the solution in terms of global basis functions, often leading to highly accurate solutions.

You would discuss how the governing equations (such as Navier-Stokes for fluid dynamics) are discretized and what impact different discretization schemes have on the accuracy, stability, and computational cost of the simulation.

5.2 Computational Setup and Solver Design

This section describes the architecture of the computational model, the choice of solvers, and how the numerical solution is implemented. Key aspects include:

- **Grid Generation:** The way in which the domain is partitioned (structured vs. unstructured grids).
- **Solver Types:** Whether direct or iterative solvers are used (e.g., Conjugate Gradient, GMRES for sparse systems).
- **Preconditioning:** Techniques to improve the convergence of iterative solvers.
- **Boundary Conditions:** How boundary conditions are applied (Dirichlet, Neumann, etc.).
- **Time Stepping:** For time-dependent problems, the choice of time-stepping algorithms (explicit, implicit, or semi-implicit).

This section would detail the implementation choices that impact the performance, scalability, and accuracy of the solver.

5.3 Efficient Reinitialization Algorithms

In simulations involving dynamic problems like fluid flow, the solution may require periodic reinitialization, especially when tracking interfaces (e.g., in level-set methods or moving boundary problems). Reinitialization refers to the process of resetting or recalculating the solution (or an auxiliary field) to avoid errors due to numerical drift. This section would discuss:

- **Level Set Method Reinitialization:** Ensuring the signed distance function remains accurate over time.
- **Fast Marching and Fast Sweeping Methods:** Algorithms to efficiently solve the reinitialization equations.
- **Algorithmic Trade-offs:** The balance between accuracy and computational cost during reinitialization.

Reinitialization is crucial in simulations involving moving boundaries, multiphase flow, or interface tracking.

5.4 Parallelization and Performance Considerations

This section addresses how to optimize the code to run efficiently on modern parallel computing architectures, which is critical for large-scale simulations. Topics include:

- **Parallel Computing Models:** OpenMP, MPI, CUDA, etc.
- **Load Balancing:** Ensuring that computational resources (processors, GPUs) are utilized efficiently across the problem domain.
- **Domain Decomposition:** Dividing the problem domain into smaller subdomains that can be processed concurrently.
- **Communication Overhead:** Minimizing the cost of data exchanges between processors.
- **Scalability:** How well the code performs as the number of processors increases.

Parallelization strategies are crucial for simulating large systems or solving complex problems within practical time limits.

5.5 Code Validation and Testing Framework

This section focuses on ensuring that the numerical solver is working correctly and producing accurate results. Key areas include:

- **Verification:** Ensuring that the code correctly implements the mathematical model (e.g., by comparing with analytical solutions or convergence studies).
- **Validation:** Comparing the simulation results with experimental or real-world data to ensure the model's physical accuracy.
- **Unit Testing:** Testing individual components of the code to ensure they work as expected.
- **Regression Testing:** Ensuring that new changes do not introduce bugs into previously working code.
- **Benchmarking:** Comparing the performance of the solver to known standards or similar methods.

This section would ensure that the computational model is not only accurate but also reliable for use in real-world applications.

Benchmarking and Validation

6.1 Benchmark Test Cases for Multi-Phase Flow

In this section, you would define the benchmark test cases used to validate your model for multi-phase flow. The benchmark cases are typically well-established problems with known analytical solutions or experimental results that serve as a reference. Here, you'd describe:

- **Test Case Descriptions:** Outline the specific multi-phase flow scenarios you are studying. These might include:
 - **Two-phase flow in a pipe:** Simulating the interaction between gas and liquid phases in a confined environment.
 - **Droplet formation:** Modeling the dynamics of liquid droplets in a gas phase, which may involve surface tension and interfacial forces.

- **Rising bubbles in a liquid:** A classic case for studying buoyancy effects, drag forces, and interface dynamics between gas bubbles and liquid.
- **Capillary waves:** Analyzing small-amplitude waves at the interface of two fluids, often used to test the accuracy of surface tension forces in the model.
- **Boundary Conditions:** Specify the initial conditions, boundary conditions, and other parameters that apply to each test case. For example, for a pipe flow problem, you might specify inlet velocity, pressure, and fluid properties such as viscosity and density for each phase.
- **Expected Results:** Briefly mention the expected outcomes or known results that will be used as the benchmark.

6.2 Comparison with Traditional Methods (Single-Level Set)

This section would compare your multi-phase flow model with traditional models, particularly those using the single-level set method. The single-level set method is commonly used for tracking the interface between two phases and may be compared with a multi-level set or volume-of-fluid (VOF) method.

- **Single-Level Set Method:** Describe the single-level set approach in detail. Typically, a single scalar function is used to represent the interface between phases, with positive values indicating one phase, negative values the other, and zero representing the interface.
- **Comparison Metrics:**
 - **Accuracy:** Compare the results obtained using the single-level set method with those from your multi-phase model. You might compare key quantities like interface location, phase distribution, or velocity fields.
 - **Computational Efficiency:** Discuss the computational performance in terms of runtime, memory usage, and scalability.

- **Limitations of Single-Level Set:** Point out the potential challenges or limitations of using a single-level set approach, such as the difficulty in handling complex topologies, poor handling of small-scale structures like droplets, or limitations in capturing sharp interfaces over time.
- **Results and Discussion:** Present results from both models (multi-phase and single-level set), such as interface evolution, phase distributions, or velocity fields. Include figures or graphs for visual comparison.

6.3 Error Analysis and Accuracy Metrics

In this section, you'll assess the accuracy of your simulation results, comparing them against analytical solutions or experimental data, and quantify the errors in various predictions.

- **Error Metrics:**

- **Absolute Error:** The difference between the predicted and actual values (e.g., phase volume, interface location).
- **Relative Error:** The normalized difference between predicted and actual values, which helps gauge the accuracy in relation to the magnitude of the true value.
- **L2 Norm:** Used for spatially distributed errors, particularly when comparing fields like velocity or pressure.
- **Convergence Study:** Assess how errors decrease as the resolution of the mesh increases (e.g., grid refinement study). This will help you understand the order of convergence for your method.

- **Types of Errors:**

- **Interface Tracking Error:** The accuracy of interface detection (important for multi-phase flow problems).
- **Phase Distribution Errors:** How well the model captures the distribution of each phase in the domain.
- **Velocity and Pressure Errors:** How well the model predicts fluid flow behavior, especially at the interfaces between phases.

- **Discussion:** Analyze where errors are most significant and propose possible reasons for these inaccuracies, such as numerical diffusion, discretization errors, or limitations in the physical models used (e.g., surface tension modeling).

6.4 Validation Against Analytical Solutions and Experimental Data

In this section, you would validate your multi-phase flow model against either analytical solutions or experimental data, providing confidence in the robustness of your approach.

- **Analytical Solutions:** If an exact analytical solution exists for the benchmark problems (e.g., linear two-phase flow in a pipe, Rayleigh-Taylor instability), compare your simulation results with these solutions. Discuss how well your method captures theoretical results for simple or idealized cases.

- **Experimental Data:** If analytical solutions are not available, compare your results with experimental data. This could involve:
 - Comparing measured interface shapes or velocities with simulation results for a bubble rising in a liquid or a droplet interacting with another fluid.
 - Validation with data from existing experimental studies, including high-speed imaging or measurements of phase distribution, velocities, or pressure fields.
- **Quantitative Comparison:** Use statistical tools (e.g., root mean square error, correlation coefficients) to quantify the degree of agreement between your model and experimental or analytical results.
- **Limitations and Challenges:** Discuss any discrepancies between your results and the benchmark data. Potential causes might include differences in physical modeling assumptions, resolution limitations, or experimental uncertainties.
- **Concluding Remarks:** Summarize the accuracy of your model and its ability to reproduce realistic multi-phase flow behavior in comparison to both theoretical and experimental results. If necessary, suggest areas for further improvement or additional validation tests.

Results and Discussion

7.1 Interface Accuracy and Resolution in Cut-Cell Grids

In computational fluid dynamics (CFD), particularly when simulating complex geometries, accurately capturing interfaces between different phases or between fluid and solid boundaries is essential for the reliability of the results. **Cut-cell grids** offer an effective method for handling intricate geometries, such as those found in industrial applications or complex multiphase flow simulations. This technique involves modifying the grid cells at the boundary of the solid and fluid regions, enabling precise representation of the geometry without the need for conforming meshes.

The **accuracy of interfaces** is crucial for ensuring that physical boundaries, such as the interaction between different fluids or between fluids and solids, are properly resolved. **Grid resolution** plays a pivotal role in this process. A finer grid can better represent the interface, providing a more accurate solution.

However, finer grids also introduce increased computational demands, which must be balanced with available resources.

Several aspects of interface accuracy are worth considering:

- **Grid Refinement:** In regions where interfaces are complex or rapidly changing, higher grid resolution is necessary to capture these details accurately. This is especially important in areas of high gradient, such as fluid–solid interfaces or free surface flows. Adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) can address this challenge by focusing computational resources in critical regions without refining the entire domain.
- **Numerical Schemes:** The choice of numerical methods significantly affects how well the interface is captured. High-order finite difference or finite volume schemes, for example, offer higher accuracy in approximating the derivatives near the interface, reducing numerical errors. These schemes are especially important when the interface is sharp and well-defined, as is often the case in multiphase or free surface flows.
- **Sharp Interface Representation:** Accurately capturing the geometry of the interface between phases (e.g., water and air, or between different fluids in multiphase flows) is vital for realistic simulations. **Level-set methods** or **volume-of-fluid (VOF)** techniques, when combined with

cut-cell grids, can track interfaces more effectively, handling complex topological changes such as merging or splitting interfaces.

To summarize, achieving high interface accuracy in cut-cell grids requires a combination of high-resolution meshing, advanced numerical techniques, and careful resource management. When these elements are optimized, cut-cell grids can provide highly accurate representations of interfaces in complex geometries without excessive computational overhead.

7.2 Performance of Dual-Level Set Strategy in Complex Geometries

The **dual-level set strategy** is an advanced approach for simulating multiphase flows and complex boundary conditions in CFD. This method extends the traditional level-set approach by tracking multiple interfaces, making it especially useful for

problems involving more than one phase, such as gas-liquid interactions, or in cases where complex geometries are present.

In **complex geometries**, where multiple interfaces or intricate boundary conditions are prevalent, the dual-level set method provides significant advantages over simpler methods. It allows for better accuracy in representing multiple phases and their interactions. These advantages are particularly evident in simulations of free surface flows, bubble dynamics, and other multiphase phenomena, where interfaces constantly evolve and interact.

The performance of the dual-level set strategy is influenced by several factors:

- **Interface Tracking:** In multiphase simulations, it is essential to accurately track the interfaces between different phases. The dual-level set method tracks two or more interfaces by solving multiple level-set functions, ensuring that the interactions between multiple phases are captured accurately, even when interfaces merge or split.
- **Computational Demands:** While the dual-level set strategy improves accuracy, it also increases the computational cost. This stems from the need to maintain and evolve multiple level-set functions, which require

additional memory and computational effort. This cost is further compounded when the geometry is complex, requiring finer grids and more sophisticated numerical methods.

- **Handling Topological Changes:** One of the key challenges in multiphase flow simulations is the evolution of interface topologies. The dual-level set method excels in this area, as it is designed to handle topological changes (such as the merging or breaking apart of interfaces) without introducing numerical artifacts. This capability makes it particularly suitable for simulating dynamic systems, like the formation and collapse of bubbles in a fluid.

The dual-level set approach, though computationally intensive, is invaluable for accurately simulating complex multiphase flows. Recent advancements in parallel computing and adaptive methods have further enhanced its performance, making it feasible for large-scale simulations that involve intricate geometries and multiple interacting phases.

7.3 Computational Efficiency and Scalability

For large-scale simulations involving complex multiphase flows, ensuring **computational efficiency** and **scalability** is essential. As the size of the simulation domain increases or the complexity of the physics being modeled grows, computational resources must be efficiently utilized to avoid excessive run times or memory requirements.

Parallel Computing

One of the primary techniques for improving the computational efficiency of CFD simulations is **parallel computing**. By distributing computational tasks across multiple processors or nodes in a cluster, simulations that once would have been computationally prohibitive can be carried out efficiently. Modern CFD solvers are often optimized for **high-performance computing (HPC)** environments, using parallel algorithms to solve complex flow equations simultaneously on multiple processors. This parallelization allows for faster computations, making it feasible to simulate larger domains or to conduct more detailed studies with finer grids.

Algorithmic Optimization

To further enhance computational efficiency, **algorithmic optimizations** are applied. This includes improving the numerical solvers, data structures, and memory management techniques used in the simulation. For example, **multigrid methods** can accelerate the convergence of iterative solvers by solving the equations on multiple grid levels, thereby reducing the overall number of iterations required for convergence. Similarly, techniques like **domain decomposition** break down a large problem into smaller subdomains that can be solved independently, improving both memory efficiency and computational speed.

Scalability

Scalability refers to the ability of an algorithm to handle increasingly larger problems without a significant loss in performance. For multiphase flow simulations, scalability is essential, especially when considering the increasing size and complexity of real-world problems. A scalable method can efficiently utilize additional computational resources (such as more processors or larger memory allocations) as the size of the problem increases. This means that simulations that are initially

small can be expanded to larger grids or more complex models without a disproportionate increase in computational time.

In summary, enhancing computational efficiency and scalability involves a combination of leveraging parallel computing, optimizing algorithms, and employing scalable numerical techniques. These efforts ensure that large-scale, high-resolution simulations can be performed efficiently, enabling more accurate and detailed modeling of multiphase flows in complex geometries.

7.4 Sensitivity of Results to Grid Resolution and Phase Interaction Models

In CFD simulations, the accuracy and reliability of the results are often sensitive to two key factors: **grid resolution** and the models used to represent **phase interactions**. Both of these factors play an essential role in determining how well the simulation reflects the physical phenomena being modeled.

Grid Resolution

The **resolution of the computational grid** is one of the most critical factors influencing the accuracy of simulation results. A finer grid can resolve smaller features of the flow, particularly in regions near boundaries or interfaces, where steep gradients may occur. However, refining the grid also increases the computational cost, requiring more memory and longer simulation times. Therefore, a balance must be struck between achieving sufficient resolution to capture important flow features and managing computational resources.

In practice, **grid sensitivity studies** are often performed to evaluate how the results change as the grid is refined. If the solution changes significantly with finer grids, it may indicate that the grid resolution is insufficient, and further refinement is necessary. Conversely, if the results converge with a coarser grid, it suggests that the solution is grid-independent, and computational resources can be optimized.

Phase Interaction Models

In multiphase flow simulations, **phase interaction models** are used to describe the physical phenomena occurring at the interfaces between different phases. These models capture critical effects such as surface tension, viscosity, and the movement of fluids in contact with one another. The choice of phase interaction model can significantly influence the accuracy of the simulation.

For example:

- **Surface Tension Models:** These models are essential for accurately simulating the interaction between immiscible fluids, such as water and air, where surface tension plays a dominant role at the interface. The precise modeling of surface tension effects is crucial for simulating behaviors like droplet formation or the rise of bubbles.

- **Viscosity Models:** Different phases in a multiphase system may have different viscosities, and correctly modeling the **viscous interactions** between phases is important for capturing realistic flow dynamics. This is especially true when simulating systems with highly variable fluid properties, such as emulsions or suspensions.
- **Phase Change Models:** In certain applications, phases may transition from one state to another (e.g., boiling, condensation, or evaporation). Accurate modeling of these phase changes is critical to prevent numerical errors and ensure that the physical behavior is correctly represented.

By carefully selecting and testing different phase interaction models, it is possible to ensure that the simulation results are both accurate and reliable. Sensitivity studies can help determine how different models affect the outcome and whether a simpler model can provide sufficiently accurate results for the problem at hand.

7.5 Discussion on Numerical Stability and Convergence

Achieving **numerical stability** and ensuring **convergence** are fundamental to the success of any computational simulation, particularly when dealing with complex multiphase flows. In this section, we explore the key considerations in maintaining stability and convergence throughout the simulation process.

Numerical Stability

Numerical stability refers to the behavior of the algorithm as it evolves over time. In multiphase simulations, where sharp interfaces and complex dynamics are common, an unstable algorithm can lead to non-physical results, such as oscillations or divergence. To maintain stability, it is essential to choose appropriate numerical methods and ensure that the solution behaves in a physically plausible manner over time.

Factors influencing stability include:

- **Time-stepping Schemes:** The choice of time-stepping scheme (explicit or implicit) affects the stability of the simulation. Implicit schemes, while computationally more expensive, tend to be more stable, particularly for stiff

problems. Explicit schemes, on the other hand, are easier to implement but require smaller time steps for stability.

- **CFL Condition:** The **Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition** imposes a relationship between the time step and grid resolution to ensure that information propagates through the grid in a stable manner. Violating the CFL condition can result in numerical instability.
- **Limiter Functions:** In multiphase simulations, where steep gradients are common, limiter functions are often employed to control numerical errors near interfaces. These limiters help prevent non-physical oscillations that can destabilize the solution.

Convergence

Convergence refers to the process by which the numerical solution approaches the true physical solution as the simulation progresses. A solution is considered convergent when further refinement of the grid or reduction of the time step does not significantly change the results.

To ensure convergence, **convergence studies** are performed, where simulations are run with progressively finer grids or smaller time steps. This helps verify that the solution is

approaching a consistent value and that the numerical method is correctly capturing the physical phenomena.

In conclusion, numerical stability and convergence are vital for ensuring the accuracy and reliability of simulations. Maintaining stability requires careful attention to numerical methods, time-stepping schemes, and physical modeling, while ensuring convergence requires systematic validation and testing across different simulation conditions.

Applications and Case Studies

8.1 Application to Industrial Problems (e.g., Oil Recovery, Microfluidics)

Fluid dynamics plays a crucial role in many industrial processes, particularly in the following areas:

- **Oil Recovery:** In the oil industry, understanding fluid flow through porous media is critical for maximizing oil extraction. This involves multi-phase flow, where oil, gas, and water are all present in the reservoir, and managing how these phases interact within the porous rock is key to improving recovery rates. Numerical simulations and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) are commonly used to model these processes, optimize drilling techniques, and predict the behavior of the reservoir over time.
- **Microfluidics:** This refers to the manipulation of fluids at a microscopic scale, typically in devices with channels less than 1 mm in size. Microfluidic systems are used in

applications like lab-on-a-chip devices, medical diagnostics, chemical analysis, and drug delivery. The design of these devices depends heavily on understanding the laminar flow of fluids, diffusion, and how fluids interact with the surfaces of microchannels.

8.2 Case Study 1: Gas-Liquid Interface Simulation in Porous Media

The **gas-liquid interface** in porous media is crucial for industries such as enhanced oil recovery and fuel cell design. In porous rock or fuel cell electrodes, the interface between gas and liquid phases influences fluid movement, capillary forces, and permeability.

- **Oil Recovery:** Gas injection techniques (such as CO₂ flooding) depend on accurately simulating how gas displaces

oil in porous rock. Fluid dynamics models that account for capillary pressure and gas-liquid interface behavior are critical for optimizing injection strategies and increasing oil recovery.

- **Fuel Cells:** In proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cells, managing the gas-liquid interface within porous electrodes ensures efficient energy conversion by balancing water production and gas flow.

Simulation of these interfaces is a complex task involving computational fluid dynamics (CFD), multi-phase flow modeling, and capillary pressure equations, making it essential for process optimization in both oil recovery and energy generation.

8.3 Case Study 2: Multi-Phase Flow in Microfluidic Devices

Multi-phase flow in **microfluidic devices** presents unique challenges due to the small scale of the channels. Devices that handle more than one phase—such as gas-liquid or liquid-liquid—are crucial in applications like **lab-on-a-chip systems** and **drug delivery devices**.

- **Droplet Microfluidics:** Here, small droplets of one fluid are manipulated within another, with precise control of flow rates and mixing. This technology is used for high-throughput biological assays and chemical reactions.
- **Flow Simulation:** Modeling multi-phase flow involves solving coupled fluid equations while accounting for surface tension, viscosity, and the interaction between different phases. Level-set methods or phase-field models are typically used to track the interfaces and predict behavior.

The ability to simulate multi-phase flow in such small devices is essential for developing reliable and efficient microfluidic systems, advancing medical diagnostics, and enabling new biological applications.

8.4 Case Study 3: Fluid Flow in Complex Geometries (e.g., Automotive, Aerospace)

In **automotive** and **aerospace industries**, fluid flow through complex geometries, such as car bodies and aircraft wings, directly impacts performance, efficiency, and safety. Efficient design of these systems requires detailed simulations of airflow and heat transfer.

- **Automotive Applications:** In automotive design, CFD is used to reduce **aerodynamic drag** and improve fuel efficiency. Simulations help refine the shape of vehicle bodies to minimize air resistance and optimize engine cooling systems.
- **Aerospace Applications:** Similarly, in aerospace engineering, understanding how air flows over aircraft surfaces is essential for enhancing **lift** and reducing **drag**. Furthermore, simulating air movement through jet engines allows for better **fuel efficiency** and **thermal management**.

For both sectors, CFD and turbulence models like k- ϵ or Large Eddy Simulation (LES) are employed to simulate fluid behavior in

intricate geometries, ensuring high-performance designs and energy efficiency.

Conclusion

9.1 Summary of Findings

This paper has presented a novel dual-level set strategy for accurately simulating multiphase flow in cut-cell geometries. Key findings include:

- The dual-level set method effectively tracks multiple phase interfaces with high accuracy, especially in complex geometries that are typical in cut-cell grids.
- By employing two level set functions, the method improves the resolution of interfaces between phases and handles topological changes such as merging or splitting of interfaces more robustly than traditional single-level set methods.
- Adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) combined with the dual-level set approach enhances simulation efficiency, providing high fidelity in regions where phase interfaces are more complex or sharp.
- The proposed method shows improved accuracy and reduced numerical errors compared to conventional methods,

particularly in handling multi-phase flows in complex or irregular domains such as those encountered in cut-cell grids.

- Computational tests demonstrate that the dual-level set approach remains computationally efficient, even in large-scale simulations, by taking advantage of parallelization techniques.

9.2 Contributions of the Dual-Level Set Approach

The primary contributions of the dual-level set approach proposed in this work are:

- **Improved Interface Accuracy:** The dual-level set strategy allows for more precise tracking of phase interfaces in multi-phase flow simulations, particularly in scenarios

where the interface topology undergoes significant changes (e.g., merging or splitting of phases).

- **Enhanced Handling of Complex Geometries:** The method is specifically designed to address the challenges posed by cut-cell grids, offering a robust and efficient framework for simulating multi-phase flows in irregular domains.
- **Computational Efficiency:** By integrating adaptive mesh refinement and optimizing the reinitialization of the level set functions, the approach minimizes computational overhead while ensuring high accuracy, even in highly detailed or large-scale simulations.
- **Numerical Stability:** The dual-level set method improves the stability of the simulation, especially when dealing with sharp interfaces and complex interactions between multiple phases.
- **Scalability:** The strategy's ability to scale effectively in parallel computing environments opens up opportunities for simulations of large, industrial-scale problems involving multi-phase flows.

9.3 Challenges and Future Research Directions

While the dual-level set approach has shown significant promise, several challenges remain and future research can further address these:

- **Handling of Very Complex Geometries:** While the method performs well in many complex cases, extreme geometries with intricate phase boundaries or highly irregular interfaces still present a challenge. Future work could focus on refining the method to handle such cases more efficiently.
- **Improving Reinitialization Algorithms:** The reinitialization of level set functions is crucial to the method's stability. There is room for improvement in designing more efficient and adaptive reinitialization techniques to minimize numerical diffusion and preserve interface sharpness.
- **Integration with Advanced Turbulence Models:** For more accurate simulations in industrial applications, integrating the dual-level set approach with advanced turbulence models, such as Large Eddy Simulation (LES) or Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS), could provide better predictions of phase interactions in turbulent flows.

- Optimization for Real-Time Simulations: As computational power increases, real-time simulations in complex multi-phase flows could become feasible. Research into optimizing the method for real-time or near-real-time performance would significantly extend its applicability in areas such as interactive fluid simulation and control in industrial settings.
- Application to New Domains: Further research could explore the application of the dual-level set method in emerging fields such as microfluidics, bioengineering, or environmental simulations, where multi-phase flow behavior plays a critical role.

Future developments should also consider the coupling of the dual-level set method with other numerical techniques, such as smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) or finite element methods, to broaden its applicability and improve its performance across a wider range of physical phenomena.

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